

Disease resistance

A promising donor for blast resistance

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Leaf blast is one of the most important rice diseases in Kerala, and Pattambi is a hot spot for the disease. While screening prerelease cultures for disease resistance, we found that KAU1907, a short-

duration, white-kerneled, medium-tall culture from the cross Bhavani/Triveni scored 1 in a trial where the national check variety Vani scored 6, using the 0-9 scale. Tests in three subsequent trials confirmed this highly resistant reaction of the culture (see table). This finding is significant because KAU1907 has wide adaptability to important seasons and cropping situations in Kerala, including rainfed uplands. □

Reaction of KAU1907 to leaf blast at Pattambi, India.

Variety	Disease score (0-9 scale)			
	1981-82		1982-83	
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 1	Trial 2
Triveni	5	5	9	7
Kannagi	9	3	7	3
Vani	6	1	1	1
KAU1907	1	0	0	0

Antibiotic activity of rice agglutinin

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Agglutination or immobilization of plant pathogenic bacteria in several hosts, including rice, has been reported. We isolated a small molecular weight protein from rice seeds and leaves that showed agglutination and antibiotic activity. The rice agglutination factor (RAF) was isolated from cultivars TN1 and BJ1. Agglutination was determined by the agglutination drop test. Antibiotic activity was

Antibiotic activity and agglutination titers of the rice agglutinin factor (RAF) derived from the seeds and leaves of some rice cultivars.^a

Source	Av diam of inhibition zones (mm) against		Agglutination titers against	
	<i>X. c. pv. oryzae</i>	<i>E. amylovora</i> (E8)	<i>X. c. pv. oryzae</i> (H470)	<i>E. amylovora</i> (E8)
TN1 seed	8	10	1:64	1:64
TN1 leaf	10	0	n.t.	n.t.
BJ1 seed	10	8	1:256	1:128
RJ1 leaf	16	7	n.t.	n.t.

^an.t. = not tested.

measured, using the cylinder-plate method, against a virulent strain of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* (H470) and an avirulent acapsular strain of *Erwinia amylovora* (E8) (see table).

The RAF derived from BJ1 had higher antibiotic activity than that from TN1.

The RAF from BJ1 seeds also was higher than that from TN1. It is likely that the RAF plays a role in the disease resistance capability of certain cultivars not only by its agglutinating activity but also by anti-biotic activity. □

Varietal resistance to leaf blast and sheath blight at Pattambi, India

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Leaf blast (Bl) and sheath blight (ShB) are two major rice diseases in Kerala. During 1981-82 kharif, 388 cultivars of National Screening Nursery I were tested for Bl and ShB resistance at RARS, Pattambi, which is a hot spot location for both diseases. Screening for Bl used UBN pattern and was under upland situations with Pusa 2-21 as the susceptible check. ShB screening was under transplanted conditions with Jyothy as susceptible

Rice cultures with multiple resistance to leaf blast and sheath blight at RARS, Pattambi, Kerala, India.

Entry	Cross	Reaction to	
		Leaf blast	Sheath blight
TNAU17005	Dasal/IR20	R	MR
RNR74822	Sona/Monoharsali	R	R
R245-30-41	OBS677/IR2078-436-3-5	R	R
HPU2205	ASH/IR1820-17-1	R	R
HPU2206	-do-	R	R
HPU2203	AS11/IR1820-210-2-//CH1039	R	R
IET6080	-do-	R	MR
RP1015-12-10-3-1-1	Sona/Monoharsali	MR	MR
R161-3179	Kali monch 64/Sona	MR	MR
KMP8	-do-	MR	MR
KMP41	-do-	MR	MR
RNR82249	Tella	hamsa/Rasi MR	MR
RP1015-45-117-1	Sona/Monoharsali	MR	MR
RP1015-38-85-1	-do-	MR	MR

check. Each test entry was planted in two 2-m rows, spaced at 20- × 15-cm. Plants were inoculated at tillering stage with the ShB pathogen multiplied on rice stem pieces. Disease reactions were judged by the Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale.

Disease pressure was high (location severity index [LSI] = 7.22) for B1 and moderate (LSI = 4.60) for ShB.

CR280-5, JR49, and MGL 14 were highly resistant to ShB and 139 entries showed resistant or moderately resistant reactions. RNR788 11, WGL 26420, and

RGL 1746 were highly resistant to B1 and 39 entries had resistant to moderately resistant reactions. Although all the six lines with highly resistant reactions to one disease were susceptible to the other disease, 14 entries resistant to both diseases were identified (see table). □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Japonica cultivars are more susceptible to brown planthopper biotype 1 than Tongil hybrids

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Susceptibility of Tongil lines (japonica/indica) with no genes for resistance to brown planthopper (BPH) was studied using a seedling bulk test. Four japonica and 4 Tongil lines that are recommended to farmers in Korea were alternately planted in 15-cm-long rows in plastic boxes with 2 replications. Cultivar reaction to BPH biotype 1 was recorded at 7, 9, 11, and 13 days after infestation (DI) using the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

Seedling reactions of selected rice cultivars to brown planthopper biotype 1.

Rice type	Variety	Damage rating ^a at given days after infestation			
		7d	9d	11 d	13 d
Tongil (japonica/ indica)	Milyang 23	R	R	MR	M
	Seogwangbyeo	R	R	MR	MS
	Pungsanbyeo	R	R	MR	MS
Japonica	Jinjubyeo	MR	M	S	S
	Dongjinbyeo	M	MS	S	S
	Samnambyeo	M	MS	S	S
	Sangpungbyeo	M	MS	S	S
	Cheongcheongbyeo (R check)	R	R	R	R

^aBased on seedling bulk test: R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, M = moderate, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible.

Japonica varieties Jinjubyeo, Dongjinbyeo, Samnambyeo, and Sangpungbyeo were susceptible to BPH at 11 DI. Tongil lines Milyang 23, Seogwangbyeo, and Pungsanbyeo were moderately resis-

tant to BPH at 11 DI (see table). Among rice cultivars with no BPH resistance genes, japonica cultivars at seedling stage were much more susceptible to BPH than Tongil lines. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Rice tolerance for coastal salinity

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Rice varieties were screened in rainfed fields for coastal soil salinity tolerance during kharif (Jun-Nov) 1980, 1981, and 1982 at CSSRI. Trials were in a randomized block design with three replications. Soil pH was 7.0 and soil salinity (ECe) ranged from 6.3 to 11.5 in 1980, 6.3 to 8.3 in 1981, and 9.4 to 16.9 mmho/cm in

1982 at different crop growth stages. One-hundred and sixty-three varieties or lines were compared to local checks CSRI and Nonasail (Sel), using the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale. Plant survival at maturity also was recorded (see table).

In 1980 Nonasail (Sel) scored best at all stages. The lines IR4432-28-5 and IR2863-35-3-3 also were promising. In 1981 10 varieties or lines scored better than the resistant check at vegetative stage. Among them, IR9884-54-3 and M152 were the most tolerant. Although IR42 had 100% survival, it had poorer growth than IR36. Lines that performed

as well as the local check CSRI were IR4432-28-5, Nonasail (Sel), IR10198-66-2, and IR2307-247-2-2-3. IR4432-28-5, Nonasail (Sel), IR10198-66-2, and CSRI exhibited more tolerance at ripening stage than at vegetative stage. IR9852-19-2 and IR13426-19-2 had better tolerance at ripening stage.

Salinity was highest in 1982 and most varieties had high mortality and poor growth. However, M152, M242, PNL 28-23, and Nonasail (Sel) had 50% survival and performed best. Tests showed that there are three levels of salt tolerance: tolerance at all growth stages, tolerance at vegetative stage, and tol-